

Deliverable D-JRP21-WP4.16

Workpackage 4

Responsible Partner: VetMedUni/
AGES (AT)

Contributing partners: APHA (UK), ANSES
(FR), BfR (DE)

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
Funding	This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.
Grant Agreement	Grant agreement n° 773830
Start Date	01/01/2018 (BIOPIGEE 01/01/2020)
Duration	60 Months (BIOPIGEE 36 months)

DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

JIP/JRP deliverable	D-JRP21-WP4.16 Economic calculation		
Project Acronym	JRP21-FBZ3.1-BIOPIGEE		
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Due month of the report	55		
Actual submission month	57		
Type <i>R: Document, report DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.; OTHER</i>	R Save date: 16-Sep-22		
Dissemination level <i>PU: Public (default) CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)</i>	PU This is the default setting. If this project deliverable should be confidential, please add justification here (may be assessed by PMT): Confidential until publication.....		
Dissemination <i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i>	OHEJP WP 1 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 2 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 3 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 4 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 5 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 6 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/> Project Management Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Communication Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Scientific Steering Board <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/> EFSA <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> ECDC <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> EEA <input type="checkbox"/> EMA <input type="checkbox"/> FAO <input type="checkbox"/> WHO <input type="checkbox"/> OIE <input type="checkbox"/> Other international stakeholder(s): Social Media: Other recipient(s): via publication		

BIOPIGEE

Economic calculation

Participating countries

Austria (AGES), United Kingdom (APHA), Germany (BfR), France (ANSES)

Background

Salmonella and Hepatitis E virus (HEV) are both important foodborne pathogens, which usually lead to subclinical infections in pigs but can cause mild to severe symptoms in humans. The financial burden on the public health sector, as well as the individual has been assessed in previous studies for *Salmonella* and has been estimated at € 90 million annual losses in the Europe Union (FCC Consortium, 2010). For HEV comparable data is not available. Implementation of effective biosecurity measures (BSM) along the pork production chain are essential mitigations to reduce the risk of transmission of the agent along the food chain and exposure of humans. Thus, BSMs have the capacity to reduce the economic impact of these foodborne pathogens.

Objective

The aim of this task was to place monetary terms on biosecurity measures proven to be effective in the reduction of *Salmonella*/ HEV to subsequently conduct an economy analysis. Different economic methods are available and have been applied to public health related research questions. To conduct a cost-benefit analysis was chosen as the most suitable method for the objective of this study. Therefore, the cost per human case was identified for each of the pathogens as well.

The economic analysis should allow farmers, producers and authorities to identify the most cost-effective mitigation measures along the pork production chain.

Methods

The effective biosecurity measures were selected from the output from BIOPIGEE WP5 , T5.2.

The initial T5.2 results presented odds ratios for the considered biosecurity measures, identified in a thorough literature review. Technical and methodological aspects of the quantitative microbial risk assessment models (QMRA) used in WP4 required risk ratios instead. Therefore, the number of considerable BSMs is lower in comparison to the measures identified in T5.2. For *Salmonella*, in total 42 measures were identified with an associated risk ratio. For 14 of these measures the risk ratio suggested positive effects in the reduction of the pathogen. For Hepatitis E only 12 measures could be considered. Only five of these measures appear to be effective in the reduction of the pathogen, according to their risk ratio. Not all as effective identified measures could be selected (14 for *Salmonella*, 5 for HEV) for the following analysis, due to technical specifications of the QMRAs and/or lack of additionally needed data.

To identify associated costs to specific biosecurity measures, definitions on their implementation were primarily taken from the original paper evaluating the effect. National biosecurity guidelines were consulted if the definition was not clear enough as well as expert opinions. Experts from the already established BIOPIGEE expert panel list were contacted. The calculations are specific for each measure unless already published estimates (i.e. rodent control) were identified.

Four European countries were chosen as examples (Austria, France, Germany and United Kingdom) for the economic analysis. While the *Salmonella*-QMRA was already parametrized for Austria and the United Kingdom, the HEV-QMRA is currently only set up for France. Parameters to run simulations for the other countries as well, are being collated. The selection of the countries, was not solely based on logistic reasons.

The United Kingdom, at the time considered in this study was still part of the European Union, does not have a national *Salmonella* surveillance system, but 189 *Salmonella* isolates could be detected in pig samples submitted to APHA in 2020. While this marks only 6% of the documented samples for that year, it must be noted that these samples were taken from pigs with clinical symptoms, where *Salmonella* was the causative agent or an incidental finding (APHA, 2021). Germany is one of the biggest pork producers in Europe (EPRS, 2020) and has an established *Salmonella* surveillance programme (QS – system). In 2019, more than 13,500 human salmonellosis cases were reported for Germany (EFSA, 2019).

While Germany is known for large pig farms with specialized farming systems, in Austria smaller non-specialized farms are more common. Hereby, we include two countries with very different characteristics in their production systems. *Salmonella* in pig is not monitored in Austria, but has to be submitted for serotype testing to AGES if detected. France is the third largest producer of pork meat in Europe and 138 salmonellosis outbreaks (19.9 % of foodborne salmonellosis outbreaks in the EU) were recorded for the year 2020 (EFSA, 2020).

Additionally, 80% of reported human HEV cases during a 10-year period could be assigned to France, Germany and the United Kingdom (EFSA, 2017).

All calculations were conducted for the year 2019 and all costs were inflated and adjusted to that year. The year 2019 was chosen, because reported cases would be most accurate for 2019 based on the concern that reports on human salmonellosis and HEV cases could have been affected by the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic in 2020 and 2021.

No standardized methodology is available to evaluate the costs of biosecurity measures. All calculations are based on country specific pig farming data, provided they were accessible from national statistic databases or European statistics. Published data, legislation documents and expert opinions were used secondary to calculate the cost for each individual biosecurity measure. Cost were evaluated for 12 biosecurity measures, proven to be effective to reduce *Salmonella* and/or HEV.

The costs are, same as the BSMs, related to a specific production stage. Unless, it is a BSM which applies to general management practices on a farm.

The cost per human case was evaluated by carrying out cost of illness studies, considering both direct (e.g. GP visits, treatments, etc.) and indirect costs (i.e loss of productivity due to absenteeism of work). The calculations for human salmonellosis cases were based on the methodology from the FCC Consortium (FCC, 2010; FCC, 2011) and were adjusted to the year 2019 and the selected example countries. An underreporting factor (FCC, 2011), a factor considering only locally acquired cases (EFSA, 2019) and a source attribution factor (Pires et al, 2011) were considered for human salmonellosis cases. The inclusion of an underreporting factor is essential to obtain the total number of community cases, which otherwise would be underestimated.

While data is available on cost of human salmonellosis (FCC, 2010; Santos et al., 2011; Niemi et al., 2019; Miller et al., 2005, Sundström et al., 2018), comparable studies are still missing for human

Hepatitis E cases. Published literature was used to determine the cost per human HEV case, distinguishing between diagnosed asymptomatic cases, diagnosed symptomatic-mild cases and diagnosed severe/chronic cases (Ankorn et al., 2019; Mangen et al., 2015; EASL, 2018). A ratio of immuno-competent versus immuno-compromised individuals (Clark et al., 2020) was applied to all reported cases to take the higher risk for severe HEV infections for people with immuno-compromising preexisting diseases into account (EASL, 2018).

To identify cases related to the pork production chain, all locally acquired Hepatitis E genotype 3 cases were included in the cost analysis, since no source attribution data is available (EFSA, 2017). Even though it is estimated that up to 2 million HEV infections occur annually in Europe (EASL, 2018), a factor considering community cases could not be applied due to lack of data.

Sequelae were not considered in these cost of illness analyses.

Results

Biosecurity measures vary in their costs and between countries. Not all outputs are directly comparable, since different units (€ / unit annually) were selected, depending on the calculations. In the end, three units: €/sow, €/slaughter pig and €/farm were identified to monetize biosecurity measures.

Three BSMs are calculated to fit the unit € x/sow (i.e. <25% cross-fostering; disinfection and vaccination- sow), four to fit € x/slaughter pig (i.e. organic acid in feed – weaner, fattener; vaccination-piglet and anal plugging) and another four BSMs as € x/farm (i.e. boot disinfection; rodent control; specific boots and vehicle disinfection).

The cost for each biosecurity measure were calculated for the year 2019, the first year of an assumed implementation, to be consistent with the year of the reported human disease cases. Because the epidemiological model does not allow an evaluation over several years, the economic analysis will also only consider one year. Since acquisition or installation costs only occur in the first year, for some biosecurity measures the cost in the following year can be expected to be lower (e.g. Sanitary Ford).

Costs were evaluated in different scenarios provided data was available. Initially for all (100%) of farms within a country, secondly for 75% of farms applying a measure and lastly for 100% of only large farms carrying out considered measure. Hereby, the ratio of small:large farms was determined based on expert opinions, individually for each of the countries.

The cost of illness analyses demonstrated that the costs per case vary between countries. Direct comparisons of the costs for each of the pathogen should be taken with care, since different methodologies were applied to calculate the costs.

Conclusion

The evaluation of cost of biosecurity measures is difficult to standardize and calculations had to be adjusted to the individual measures. Lack of data demands the use of expert opinions and estimated values, which increases the uncertainty of the results. Collaborations on establishing standardized evaluation procedures for cost of biosecurity measures on livestock farms should be considered for future research.

Future work

Based on these results an economic cost-benefit analysis will be conducted, to evaluate the most cost-efficient biosecurity measure to reduce human salmonellosis / HEV cases. The cost-benefit analysis will use the outcomes of BIOPIGEE WP4.2/4.3. The effect of the selected biosecurity measures on human case numbers and prevalence in slaughter pigs will be evaluated using established pathogen-specific QMRAs.

Benefits considered in the economic analysis will be the savings associated to the reduced number of human cases, thus avoided human cases and lower prevalences in pigs with their resulting lower costs due to fewer infections in animals. These benefits will be compared to the cost of the biosecurity measure effecting this reduction (= costs). Benefits due to avoided product recalls are not considered at the moment, but efforts are made to consider these in future calculations. The results of the economic analysis will help to guide decision makers to choose cost-effective mitigation measures.

A publication of the evaluated cost of biosecurity measures and results of the cost of illness analysis, as well as the economic analysis is under preparation.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.

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